

Atherosclerosis, Friction, and Cardiac Afterload

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Abstract

Diffuse arterial atherosclerosis is associated with multiple plaques and lesions on the endothelial surface, which cause the surface to be rough and irregular. Kinetic friction generated by the blood flow over these irregular surfaces in diseased arteries has not been well studied.

A model is presented which includes the coefficient of friction, the normal force, the gravity force, the frictional force, and the direction of blood flow.

An increased coefficient of friction due to rough surfaces increases the frictional force (opposite the direction of blood flow) which increases afterload.

Diffuse atherosclerosis may be associated with increased afterload.

Keywords: *Atherosclerosis, friction, afterload.*

Introduction:

Kinetic friction is the friction that is generated when the undersurface of a moving object slides over the upper surface of a stationary object. The frictional force (F_k) is given by the equation:

$$F_k = \mu_c (F_n)$$

where F_n is the normal force (the weight of the object--heavier objects cause more friction than lighter objects), F_k is the frictional force (which is exerted in the opposite direction that the object is moving), F_g is the force of gravity, and μ_c is the coefficient of friction (a measure of the roughness between the two surfaces--glass moving on a rough dry surface has a μ_c of 0.4, while glass moving over a smooth greased surface would have a μ_c of 0.09, and thus a lower frictional force). [1,2]

Methods and Results:

A model is presented (see Figure 1) which illustrates all these considerations in a large artery.

In a normal aorta or other large artery with a smooth plaque free endothelium, the friction between the blood moving along the endothelial surface would be low, and the μ_c and F_k would also be low. In a diffusely diseased artery with a rough surface and extensive plaques, the μ_c and F_k would be higher. [3] Given that the frictional force would be exerted in the opposite direction of the blood (back toward the heart), the afterload that the left ventricle sees would be increased.

Other blood conditions may also increase the frictional force. [4] Increased blood viscosity or paraproteinemia, might increase the weight of the blood over the surface endothelium, increasing the normal force and thus the frictional force, while polycythemia or thrombocytosis might increase the coefficient of friction and thus increase the frictional force. Thus, such conditions may also increase cardiac afterload, putting patient at risk for complications [5].

Figure 1. Schematic of atherosclerotic arterial wall, blood flow, related forces.

Discussion:

Increased kinetic friction associated with diffuse arterial atherosclerosis, may result in increased cardiac afterload and the adverse effects thereof. Afterload reduction might be a consideration for patients with significant disease.

References:

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